

Introduction to Interval-valued Neutrosophic Subring

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Abstract. The main purpose of this article is to develop and study the notion of interval-valued neutrosophic subring. Also, we have studied some homomorphic characteristics of interval-valued neutrosophic subring. Again, we have defined the concept of product of two interval-valued neutrosophic subrings and analyzed some of its important properties. Furthermore, we have developed the notion of interval-valued neutrosophic normal subring and studied some of its basic characteristics and homomorphic properties.

Keywords: Neutrosophic set; Interval-valued neutrosophic set; Interval-valued neutrosophic subring; Interval-valued neutrosophic normal subring

ABBREVIATIONS

TN signifies “T-norm”.

SN signifies “S-norm”.

IVTN signifies “interval-valued T-norm”.

IVSN signifies “interval-valued S-norm”.

CS signifies “crisp set”.

FS signifies “fuzzy set”.

IFS signifies “intuitionistic fuzzy set”.

NS signifies “neutrosophic set”.

PS signifies “plithogenic set”.

FSG signifies “fuzzy subgroup”.

IFSG signifies “intuitionistic fuzzy subgroup”.

NSG signifies “neutrosophic subgroup”.

CR signifies “crisp ring”.

FSR signifies “fuzzy subring”.

IFSR signifies “intuitionistic fuzzy subring”.

NSR signifies “neutrosophic subring”.

IVFSR signifies “interval-valued fuzzy subring”.

IVIFSR signifies “interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy subring”.

IVNSR signifies “interval-valued neutrosophic subring”.

IVNNSR signifies “interval-valued neutrosophic normal subring”.

DMP signifies “decision making problem”.

$\psi(P)$ signifies “power set of P ”.

L signifies “the set $[0, 1]$ ”.

1. Introduction

Zadeh’s vision behind introducing the revolutionary concept of FS [1] theory was to tackle uncertainty in a better way than CS theory, which has certain drawbacks. Later on, following his vision Atanassov introduced a more general version of it, which is known as IFS [2] theory. These IFSs are a little step ahead in managing ambiguities and hence are welcomed by numerous researchers. Furthermore, following their footsteps Smarandache introduced NS [3] theory, which is more capable of handling vague situations. It is a significant generalization over CS, FS, and IFS theories. Smarandache has also initiated the concept of PS [4] theory which has broader aspects than those previously discussed concepts. In NS and PS theory, he has also developed the notions of neutrosophic calculus [5], neutrosophic probability [6], neutrosophic statistics [7], integral, measure [8], neutrosophic psychology [9], neutrosophic robotics [10], neutrosophic triplet group [11], plithogenic hypersoft set [12], plithogenic fuzzy whole hypersoft set [13], plithogenic logic, probability [14], plithogenic subgroup [15], plithogenic hypersoft subgroup [16], etc. Again, NS theory has various other contributions in different scientific researches, like in linear programming [17–20], decision making [21–27], healthcare [28,29], shortest path problem [30–37], neutrosophic forecasting [38], resource leveling [39], transportation problem [40,41], project scheduling [42], brain processing [43], etc.

Gradually, interval-valued versions of FS [44], IFS [45], and NS [46] were introduced, which are further generalizations of their CS, FS, IFS, and NS counterparts. Presently, these set theories are extensively used in different scientific domains. From the very start, various researchers have carried out this concepts and explored them in different dimensions. In the subsequent Table 1 we have referred some significant aspects of these notions.

TABLE 1. Importance of interval-valued notions in different domains.

Author & references	Year	Contributions in various fields
Biswas [47]	1994	Introduced interval-valued FSG.

continued ...

Author & references	Year	Contributions in various fields
Atanassov [45]	1999	Studied basic definition and some properties of IVFS.
Mondal & Samanta [48]	2001	Defined and studied topology of IVIFSs.
Wang et al. [46]	2005	Proposed and studied IVNS and interval-valued neutrosophic logic.
Ye [49]	2009	Worked on multi-criteria DMP under IVIFSs.
Kang & Hur [50]	2010	Introduced and studied the notion of IVFSR.
Akram & Dudek [51]	2011	Defined some basic operations on interval-valued fuzzy graphs and studied some of their properties.
Aygünoğlu et al. [52]	2012	Introduced interval-valued IFSG and studied some homomorphic properties of it.
Moorthy & Arjunan [53]	2014	Introduced and studied some properties of IVIFSR.
Aiwu et al. [54]	2015	Worked on multi-attribute DMP under IVNSs.
Broumi et al. [56]	2016	Worked on interval-valued neutrosophic graph theory.
Deli [55]	2017	Applied soft version of IVNS in DMP.
Broumi et al. [56]	2019	Studied some properties of interval-valued neutrosophic graphs.

Group theory and ring theory are fundamental building blocks of abstract algebra, which are utilized in different scientific domains. But, initially, these concepts were introduced upon crisp environment. Gradually, from 1971 on-wards researchers started introducing these concepts under various uncertain environments. Some significant developments of these notions under uncertainty are the concepts of FSG [57], IFSG [58], NSG [59], FSR [60,61], IFSR [62], NSR [63], etc. Again some researchers have introduced these concepts under interval-valued environments and initiated the notions of interval-valued FSG [47], interval-valued IFSG [52], interval-valued NSG [64], interval-valued FSR [50], interval-valued IFSR [53], etc. Some more articles which can be helpful to different researchers are [65–71], etc. But, still, the notion of interval-valued NSR is undefined. Hence, by mixing interval-valued environment with neutrosophic environment, we can introduce a more general version of NSR, which will be called IVNSR. Also, their homomorphic properties can be studied. Again, their product and normal forms can be developed and analyzed. Based on these observations, the followings are some of our main objectives for this article:

- Introducing the notion of IVNSR and a analyzing its homomorphic properties.
- Introducing the product of IVNSRs.
- Introducing subring of a IVNSR.

- Introducing the notion of IVNNSR and analyzing its homomorphic attributes.

The subsequent arrangement of this article is: in Section 2, some desk researches of FS, IFS, NS, IVFS, IVIFS, IVNS, FSR, IFSR, NSR, IVFSR, IVIFSR, etc., are discussed. In Section 3, the idea of IVNSR has been introduced and some basic theories are provided. Also, their product and normal versions are defined. Also, some theories are given to understand their algebraic attributes. Lastly, in Section 4, the concluding segment is given and also some opportunities for further studies are mentioned.

2. Literature Review

Definition 2.1. [1] A FS of a CS P is defined as the function $\nu : P \rightarrow L$.

Definition 2.2. [2] An IFS ρ of a CS P is defined as $\rho = \{(r, t_\rho(r), f_\rho(r)) : r \in P\}$, where $\forall r \in P$, $t_\rho(r)$ and $f_\rho(r)$ known as the degree of membership and non-membership which satisfy the inequality $0 \leq t_\rho(r) + f_\rho(r) \leq 1$.

Definition 2.3. [3] A NS κ of a CS P is defined as $\kappa = \{(r, t_\kappa(r), i_\kappa(r), f_\kappa(r)) : r \in P\}$, where $\forall r \in P$, $t_\kappa(r)$, $i_\kappa(r)$, and $f_\kappa(r)$ are known as degree of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity which satisfy the inequality $-0 \leq t_\kappa(r) + i_\kappa(r) + f_\kappa(r) \leq 3^+$.

Definition 2.4. [52] An interval number of $L = [0, 1]$ is denoted as $\bar{k} = [k^-, k^+]$, where $1 \geq k^+ \geq k^- \geq 0$.

Definition 2.5. [44] An IVFS of P is defined as the mapping $\nu : P \rightarrow \psi(L)$.

Definition 2.6. [45] An IVIFS of P is defined as the mapping $\bar{\rho} : P \rightarrow \psi(L) \times \psi(L)$, It is denoted as $\bar{\rho} = \{(r, \bar{t}_\rho(r), \bar{f}_\rho(r)) : r \in P\}$, where $\bar{t}_\rho(r), \bar{f}_\rho(r) \subseteq [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.7. [46] An IVNS of P is defined as the mapping $\bar{\kappa} : P \rightarrow \psi(L) \times \psi(L) \times \psi(L)$, It is denoted as $\bar{\kappa} = \{(r, \bar{t}_\kappa(r), \bar{i}_\kappa(r), \bar{f}_\kappa(r)) : r \in P\}$ where $\forall r \in P$, $\bar{t}_\kappa(r), \bar{i}_\kappa(r)$, and $\bar{f}_\kappa(r) \subseteq L$.

Definition 2.8. [46] Let $\bar{\kappa}_1 = \{(r, \bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}(r), \bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}(r), \bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}(r)) : r \in P\}$ and $\bar{\kappa}_2 = \{(r, \bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}(r), \bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}(r), \bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}(r)) : r \in P\}$ be two IVNSs of P . Then union of $\bar{\kappa}_1$ and $\bar{\kappa}_2$ is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_1 \cup \bar{\kappa}_2} &= [\max \{\bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^-, \bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^-\}, \max \{\bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^+, \bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^+\}] \\ \bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_1 \cup \bar{\kappa}_2} &= [\min \{\bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^-, \bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^-\}, \min \{\bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^+, \bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^+\}] \\ \bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_1 \cup \bar{\kappa}_2} &= [\min \{\bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^-, \bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^-\}, \min \{\bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^+, \bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^+\}] \end{aligned}$$

Then intersection of $\bar{\kappa}_1$ and $\bar{\kappa}_2$ is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_1 \cap \bar{\kappa}_2} &= [\min \{\bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^-, \bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^-\}, \min \{\bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^+, \bar{t}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^+\}] \\ \bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_1 \cap \bar{\kappa}_2} &= [\max \{\bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^-, \bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^-\}, \max \{\bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^+, \bar{i}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^+\}] \\ \bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_1 \cap \bar{\kappa}_2} &= [\max \{\bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^-, \bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^-\}, \max \{\bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_1}^+, \bar{f}_{\bar{\kappa}_2}^+\}] \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.9. [72] A function $T : L \rightarrow L$ is called a TN iff $\forall r, v, z \in L$, the followings can be concluded

- (i) $T(r, 1) = r$
- (ii) $T(r, v) = T(v, r)$
- (iii) $T(r, v) \leq T(z, v)$ if $r \leq z$
- (iv) $T(r, T(v, z)) = T(T(r, v), z)$

Definition 2.10. [73] A function $\bar{T} : \psi(L) \times \psi(L) \rightarrow \psi(L)$ defined as $\bar{T}(\bar{k}, \bar{w}) = [T(k^-, w^-), T(k^+, w^+)]$, where T is a TN is known as an IVTN.

Definition 2.11. [72] A function $S : L \rightarrow L$ is called a SN iff $\forall r, v, z \in L$, the followings can be concluded

- (i) $S(r, 0) = r$
- (ii) $S(r, v) = S(v, r)$
- (iii) $S(r, v) \leq S(z, v)$ if $r \leq z$
- (iv) $S(r, S(v, z)) = S(S(r, v), z)$

Definition 2.12. [73] The function $\bar{S} : \psi(L) \times \psi(L) \rightarrow \psi(L)$ defined as $\bar{S}(\bar{k}, \bar{w}) = [S(k^-, w^-), S(k^+, w^+)]$, where S is a SN is called an IVSN.

2.1. Fuzzy, Intuitionistic fuzzy & Neutrosophic subrings

Definition 2.13. [60] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring. A FS λ is called a FSR of P , iff $\forall r, v \in P$,

- (i) $\lambda(r - v) \geq \min\{\lambda(r), \lambda(v)\}$,
- (ii) $\lambda(r \cdot v) \geq \min\{\lambda(r), \lambda(v)\}$

The set of all FSR of a crisp ring $(P, +, \cdot)$ will be denoted as $\text{FSR}(P)$.

Theorem 2.1. [61] Any FS λ of a ring $(P, +, \cdot)$ is a FSR of P iff the level sets λ_s ($\lambda(\theta_P) \geq s \geq 0$) are crisp subrings of P , where θ_P is the zero element of P .

Definition 2.14. [61] Let λ be a FSR of $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $\lambda(\theta_P) \geq s \geq 0$, where θ_P is the zero element of P . Then λ_s is called a level subring of λ .

Proposition 2.2. [61] Let $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in \text{FSR}(P)$. Then $\lambda_1 \cap \lambda_2 \in \text{FSR}(P)$.

Theorem 2.3. [61] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings. Also, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a homomorphism. If λ is a FSR of P then $l(\lambda)$ is a FSR of R .

Theorem 2.4. [61] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings. Also, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a homomorphism. If λ' is a FSR of R then $l^{-1}(\lambda')$ is a FSR of P .

Definition 2.15. [62] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring. An IFS $\gamma = \{(r, t_\gamma(r), f_\gamma(r)) : r \in P\}$ is called an IFSR of P , iff $\forall r, v \in P$,

- (i) $t_\gamma(r + v) \geq T(t_\gamma(r), t_\gamma(v)), f_\gamma(r + v) \leq S(f_\gamma(r), i_\gamma(v))$
- (ii) $t_\gamma(-r) \geq t_\gamma(r), f_\gamma(-r) \leq f_\gamma(r)$
- (iii) $t_\gamma(r \cdot v) \geq T(t_\gamma(r), t_\gamma(v)), f_\gamma(r \cdot v) \leq S(f_\gamma(r), i_\gamma(v))$.

Here, T is a TN and S is a SN.

The set of all IFSR of a crisp ring $(P, +, \cdot)$ will be denoted as $\text{IFSR}(P)$.

Proposition 2.5. [62] Let $\gamma \in \text{IFSR}(P)$. Then the followings will hold

- (i) $t_\gamma(-r) = t_\gamma(r), f_\gamma(-r) = f_\gamma(r)$ and
- (ii) $t_\gamma(\theta_P) \geq t_\gamma(r), f_\gamma(\theta_P) \leq f_\gamma(r)$, where θ_P is the zero element of P .

Proposition 2.6. [62] An IFS $\gamma = \{(r, t_\gamma(r), f_\gamma(r)) : r \in P\}$ is called an IFSR of P , iff $\forall r, v \in P$,

- (i) $t_\gamma(r - v) \geq T(t_\gamma(r), t_\gamma(v)), f_\gamma(r - v) \leq S(f_\gamma(r), f_\gamma(v))$
- (ii) $t_\gamma(r \cdot v) \geq T(t_\gamma(r), t_\gamma(v)), f_\gamma(r \cdot v) \leq S(f_\gamma(r), f_\gamma(v))$

Proposition 2.7. [62] Let $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in \text{IFSR}(P)$. Then $\gamma_1 \cap \gamma_2 \in \text{IFSR}(P)$.

Theorem 2.8. [62] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings. Also, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a homomorphism. If γ is an IFSR of P then $l(\gamma)$ is an IFSR of R .

Theorem 2.9. [62] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings. Also, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a homomorphism. If γ' is an IFSR of R then $l^{-1}(\gamma')$ is an IFSR of P .

Definition 2.16. [63] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring. A NS $\omega = \{(r, t_\omega(r), i_\omega(r), f_\omega(r)) : r \in P\}$ is called a NSR of P , iff $\forall r, v \in P$,

- (i) $t_\omega(r + v) \geq T(t_\omega(r), t_\omega(v)), i_\omega(r + v) \geq I(i_\omega(r), i_\omega(v)), f_\omega(r + v) \leq F(f_\omega(r), f_\omega(v))$
- (ii) $t_\omega(-r) \geq t_\omega(r), i_\omega(-r) \geq i_\omega(r), f_\omega(-r) \leq f_\omega(r)$
- (iii) $t_\omega(r \cdot v) \geq T(t_\omega(r), t_\omega(v)), i_\omega(r \cdot v) \geq I(i_\omega(r), i_\omega(v)), f_\omega(r \cdot v) \leq S(f_\omega(r), f_\omega(v))$.

Here, T and I are two TNs and S is a SN.

The set of all NSR of a crisp ring $(P, +, \cdot)$ will be denoted as $\text{NSR}(P)$.

Proposition 2.10. [63] A NS $\omega = \{(r, t_\omega(r), i_\omega(r), f_\omega(r)) : r \in P\}$ is called a NSR of P , iff $\forall r, v \in P$,

- (i) $t_\omega(r - v) \geq T(t_\omega(r), t_\omega(v)), i_\omega(r - v) \geq I(i_\omega(r), i_\omega(v)), f_\omega(r - v) \leq F(f_\omega(r), f_\omega(v))$
- (ii) $t_\omega(r \cdot v) \geq T(t_\omega(r), t_\omega(v)), i_\omega(r \cdot v) \geq I(i_\omega(r), i_\omega(v)), f_\omega(r \cdot v) \leq S(f_\omega(r), f_\omega(v))$.

Here, T and I are two TNs and S is a SN.

Proposition 2.11. [63] Let $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in NSR(P)$. Then $\omega_1 \cap \omega_2 \in NSR(P)$.

Theorem 2.12. [63] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings. Also, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a homomorphism. If ω is a NSR of P then $l(\omega)$ is a NSR of R .

Theorem 2.13. [63] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings. Also, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a homomorphism. If ω' is a NSR of R then $l^{-1}(\omega')$ is a NSR of P .

Definition 2.17. [63] Let $\omega = \{(r, t_\omega(r), i_\omega(r), f_\omega(r)) : r \in P\}$ be a NSR of P . Then $\forall s \in [0, 1]$ the s -level sets of P are defined as

- (i) $(t_\omega)_s = \{r \in P : t_\omega(r) \geq s\}$,
- (ii) $(i_\omega)_s = \{r \in P : i_\omega(r) \geq s\}$, and
- (iii) $(f_\omega)^s = \{r \in P : f_\omega(r) \leq s\}$.

Proposition 2.14. [63] A NS $\omega = \{(r, t_\omega(r), i_\omega(r), f_\omega(r)) : r \in P\}$ of a crisp ring $(P, +, \cdot)$ is a NSR of P iff $\forall s \in [0, 1]$ the s -level sets of P , i.e. $(t_\omega)_s$, $(i_\omega)_s$, and $(f_\omega)^s$ are crisp rings of P .

2.2. Interval-valued Fuzzy and intuitionistic fuzzy subrings

Definition 2.18. [50] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring. An IVFS $\Lambda = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Lambda(r)) : r \in P\}$ is called an IVFSR of $(P, +, \cdot)$ with respect to IVTN \bar{T} if $\forall r, v \in P$, the followings can be concluded:

- (i) $\bar{t}_\Lambda(r + v) \geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Lambda(r), \bar{t}_\Lambda(v))$,
- (ii) $\bar{t}_\Lambda(-r) \geq \Lambda(r)$, and
- (iii) $\bar{t}_\Lambda(r \cdot v) \geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Lambda(r), \bar{t}_\Lambda(v))$,

The set of all IVFSR of a crisp ring $(P, +, \cdot)$ with respect to an IVTN \bar{T} will be denoted as $IVFSR(P, \bar{T})$.

Proposition 2.15. [50] Let $\lambda = \{(r, t_\lambda(r)) : r \in P\}$ be a FSR of $(P, +, \cdot)$. Then $\Lambda = [t_\lambda, t_\lambda]$ is an IVFSR of P .

Proposition 2.16. [50] Let $\Lambda = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Lambda(r)) : r \in P\}$ be an IVFSR of $(P, +, \cdot)$. Then $\Lambda^- = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Lambda^-(r)) : r \in P\}$ and $\Lambda^+ = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Lambda^+(r)) : r \in P\}$ are FSRs of P .

Definition 2.19. [53] Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring. An IVIFS $\Gamma = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Gamma(r), \bar{f}_\Gamma(r)) : r \in P\}$ is called an IVIFSR of $(P, +, \cdot)$ if $\forall r, v \in P$, the followings can be concluded:

- (i) $\bar{t}_\Gamma(r + v) \geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Gamma(r), \bar{t}_\Gamma(v))$, $\bar{f}_\Gamma(r + v) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Gamma(r), \bar{f}_\Gamma(v))$,
- (ii) $\bar{t}_\Gamma(-r) \geq \bar{t}_\Gamma(r)$, $\bar{f}_\Gamma(-r) \leq \bar{f}_\Gamma(r)$, and
- (iii) $\bar{t}_\Gamma(r \cdot v) \geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Gamma(r), \bar{t}_\Gamma(v))$, $\bar{f}_\Gamma(r \cdot v) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Gamma(r), \bar{f}_\Gamma(v))$.

The set of all IVIFSR of a crisp ring $(P, +, \cdot)$ will be denoted as $IVIFSR(P)$.

Theorem 2.17. [53] If $\Gamma = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Gamma(r), \bar{f}_\Gamma(r)) : r \in P\} \in IVIFSR(P)$, then $\bar{t}_\Gamma(r) \leq \bar{t}_\Gamma(\theta_P)$ and $\bar{f}_\Gamma(r) \geq \bar{f}_\Gamma(\theta_P)$.

Theorem 2.18. [53] If Γ_1 and $\Gamma_2 \in IVIFSR(P)$, then $\Gamma_1 \cap \Gamma_2 \in IVIFSR(P)$.

Theorem 2.19. [53] Let $\Gamma = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Gamma(r), \bar{f}_\Gamma(r)) : r \in P\} \in IVIFSR(P)$, then $\forall r, v \in P$

- (i) $\bar{t}_\Gamma(r - v) = \bar{t}_\Gamma(\theta_P)$ implies that $\bar{t}_\Gamma(r) = \bar{t}_\Gamma(v)$.
- (ii) $\bar{f}_\Gamma(r - v) = \bar{f}_\Gamma(\theta_P)$ implies that $\bar{f}_\Gamma(r) = \bar{f}_\Gamma(v)$.

3. Proposed notion of interval-valued neutrosophic subring

Definition 3.1. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring. An IVNS $\Omega = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(r)) : r \in P\}$ is called an IVNSR of $(P, +, \cdot)$ if $\forall r, v \in P$, the followings can be concluded:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(i)} \quad & \begin{cases} \bar{t}_\Omega(r + v) \geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)), \\ \bar{i}_\Omega(r + v) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(v)), \\ \bar{f}_\Omega(r + v) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(v)) \end{cases} \\
 \text{(ii)} \quad & \begin{cases} \bar{t}_\Omega(-r) \geq \bar{t}_\Omega(r), \\ \bar{i}_\Omega(-r) \leq \bar{i}_\Omega(r), \\ \bar{f}_\Omega(-r) \leq \bar{f}_\Omega(r) \end{cases} \\
 \text{(iii)} \quad & \begin{cases} \bar{t}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)), \\ \bar{i}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(v)), \\ \bar{f}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(v)), \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

where \bar{T} is an IVTN, \bar{I} and \bar{F} are two IVSNs.

The set of all IVNSR of a crisp ring $(P, +, \cdot)$ will be denoted as $IVNSR(P)$.

Example 3.2. Let $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ be the ring of integers with respect to usual addition and multiplication. Let $\Omega = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(r)) : r \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ be an IVNS of \mathbb{Z} , where $\forall r \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{t}_\Omega(r) &= \begin{cases} [0.2, 0.25] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} \\ [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}, \\
 \bar{i}_\Omega(r) &= \begin{cases} [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} \\ [0.1, 0.12] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}, \text{ and} \\
 \bar{f}_\Omega(r) &= \begin{cases} [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} \\ [0.75, 0.8] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, if we consider minimum TN and maximum SNs, then $\Omega \in IVNSR(\mathbb{Z})$.

Example 3.3. Let $(\mathbb{Z}_4, +, \cdot)$ be the ring of integers modulo 4 with usual addition and multiplication. Let $\Omega = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(r)) : r \in \mathbb{Z}_4\}$ be an IVNS of \mathbb{Z}_4 , where interval-valued memberships of elements belonging to Ω are mentioned in Table 2.

TABLE 2. Membership values of elements belonging to Ω

Ω	\bar{t}_Ω	\bar{i}_Ω	\bar{f}_Ω
$\bar{0}$	[0.6, 0.7]	[0.33, 0.35]	[0.2, 0.3]
$\bar{1}$	[0.7, 0.8]	[0.21, 0.23]	[0.5, 0.6]
$\bar{2}$	[0.75, 0.85]	[0.24, 0.26]	[0.3, 0.7]
$\bar{3}$	[0.75, 0.9]	[0.31, 0.33]	[0.5, 0.7]

Now, if we consider the Łukasiewicz T-norm ($T(r, v) = \max\{0, r + v - 1\}$) and bounded sum S-norms ($S(r, v) = \min\{r + v, 1\}$), then $\Omega \in \text{IVNSR}(\mathbb{Z}_4)$.

Proposition 3.1. An IVNS $\Omega = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(r)) : r \in P\}$ of a crisp ring $(P, +, \cdot)$ is an IVNSR iff the followings can be concluded (assuming that all the IVTN and IVSNs are idempotent):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(i)} \quad & \begin{cases} \bar{t}_\Omega(r - v) \geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)), \\ \bar{i}_\Omega(r - v) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(v)), \\ \bar{f}_\Omega(r - v) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(v)) \end{cases} \\
 \text{(ii)} \quad & \begin{cases} \bar{t}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)), \\ \bar{i}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(v)), \\ \bar{f}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(v)). \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let $\Omega \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{t}_\Omega(r - v) &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(-v)) \text{ [by condition (i) of Definition 3.1]} \\
 &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)) \text{ [by condition (ii) of Definition 3.1]}
 \end{aligned}$$

Similary, we will have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{i}_\Omega(r - v) &\leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(v)), \text{ and} \\
 \bar{f}_\Omega(r - v) &\leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(v)),
 \end{aligned}$$

which proves (i).

Again, (ii) follows immediately from condition (iii) of Definition 3.1.

Conversely, let (i) and (ii) of Proposition 3.1 hold. Also, let θ_P be the additive neutral element

in $(P, +, \cdot)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{t}_\Omega(\theta_P) &= \bar{t}_\Omega(r - r) \\ &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(r)) \\ &= \bar{t}_\Omega(r)\end{aligned}\tag{3.1}$$

Similarly, we can show that

$$\bar{i}_\Omega(\theta_P) \leq \bar{i}_\Omega(r)\tag{3.2}$$

$$\bar{f}_\Omega(\theta_P) \leq \bar{f}_\Omega(r)\tag{3.3}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{t}_\Omega(-r) &= \bar{t}_\Omega(\theta_P - r) \\ &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(\theta_P), \bar{t}_\Omega(r)) \\ &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(r)) \text{ [by 3.1]} \\ &= \bar{t}_\Omega(r) \text{ [since } \bar{T} \text{ is idempotent]}\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

Similarly, we can prove

$$\bar{i}_\Omega(-r) \leq \bar{i}_\Omega(r) \text{ [since } \bar{I} \text{ is idempotent]}\tag{3.5}$$

$$\bar{f}_\Omega(-r) \leq \bar{f}_\Omega(r) \text{ [since } \bar{F} \text{ is idempotent]}\tag{3.6}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{t}_\Omega(r + v) &= \bar{t}_\Omega(r - (-v)) \\ &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(-v)) \\ &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)) \text{ [by 3.4]}\end{aligned}\tag{3.7}$$

Similarly,

$$\bar{i}_\Omega(r + v) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)) \text{ [by 3.5]}\tag{3.8}$$

$$\bar{f}_\Omega(r + v) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)) \text{ [by 3.6]}\tag{3.9}$$

So, by Equations 3.7, 3.8, and 3.9 condition (i) of Proposition 3.1 has been proved. Also, condition (ii) of Proposition 3.1 is same as condition (iii) of Definition 3.1. Hence, $\Omega \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$. \square

Theorem 3.2. *Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring. If $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$, then $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$ (assuming all the IVTN and IVSNs are idempotent).*

Proof. Let $\Omega = \Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2$. Now, $\forall r, v \in P$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_\Omega(r + v) &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r + v), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r + v)) \\ &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(v)), \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v))) \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(v)), \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r))) \quad [\text{as } \bar{T} \text{ is commutative}] \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r)), \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(v), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v))) \quad [\text{as } \bar{T} \text{ is associative}] \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)) \end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

Similarly, as both \bar{I} and \bar{S} are commutative as well as associative, we will have

$$\bar{i}_\Omega(r + v) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(v)) \tag{3.11}$$

$$\bar{f}_\Omega(r + v) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(v)) \tag{3.12}$$

Again,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_\Omega(-r) &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(-r), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(-r)) \\ &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r)) \quad [\text{by Definition 3.1}] \\ &= \bar{t}_\Omega(r) \end{aligned} \tag{3.13}$$

Also,

$$\bar{i}_\Omega(-r) \leq \bar{i}_\Omega(r) \tag{3.14}$$

$$\bar{f}_\Omega(-r) \leq \bar{f}_\Omega(r) \tag{3.15}$$

Similarly, we can show that

$$\bar{t}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)), \tag{3.16}$$

$$\bar{i}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(v)), \text{ and} \tag{3.17}$$

$$\bar{f}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(v)) \tag{3.18}$$

Hence, by Equations 3.10–3.18 $\Omega = \Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$. \square

Remark 3.3. In general, if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$, then $\Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2$ may not always be an IVNSR of $(P, +, \cdot)$.

The following Example 3.4 will prove our claim.

Example 3.4. Let $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ be the ring of integers with respect to usual addition and multiplication. Let $\Omega_1 = \{(r, \bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{i}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{f}_{\Omega_1}(r)) : r \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ and $\Omega_2 = \{(r, \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r), \bar{i}_{\Omega_2}(r), \bar{f}_{\Omega_2}(r)) :$

$r \in \mathbb{Z}$ be two IVNSs of \mathbb{Z} , where $\forall r \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r) &= \begin{cases} [0.25, 0.4] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} \\ [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}, \\ \bar{i}_{\Omega_1}(r) &= \begin{cases} [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} \\ [0.17, 0.2] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}, \text{ and} \\ \bar{f}_{\Omega_1}(r) &= \begin{cases} [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} \\ [0.33, 0.4] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}. \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r) &= \begin{cases} [0.5, 0.67] & \text{if } r \in 3\mathbb{Z} \\ [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 3\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}, \\ \bar{i}_{\Omega_2}(r) &= \begin{cases} [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 3\mathbb{Z} \\ [0.2, 0.25] & \text{if } r \in 3\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}, \text{ and} \\ \bar{f}_{\Omega_2}(r) &= \begin{cases} [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 3\mathbb{Z} \\ [0.33, 0.5] & \text{if } r \in 3\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, if we consider minimum TN and maximum SNs, then $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(\mathbb{Z})$.

Now let $\Omega = \Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2$. Then for $r = 4$ and $v = 9$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r + v) &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(4 + 9) \\ &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(13) \\ &= \max\{\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(13), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(13)\} \\ &= \max\{[0, 0], [0, 0]\} \\ &= [0, 0] \end{aligned}$$

Again, if $\Omega \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$, then $\forall r, v \in P$, $\bar{t}_{\Omega}(r + v) \geq \min\{\bar{t}_{\Omega}(r), \bar{t}_{\Omega}(v)\}$. But, here for $r = 4$ and $v = 9$, $\min\{\bar{t}_{\Omega}(4), \bar{t}_{\Omega}(9)\} = \min\{[0.25, 0.4], [0.5, 0.67]\} = [0.25, 0.4] \not\geq [0, 0] = \bar{t}_{\Omega}(4 + 9)$. Hence, $\Omega \notin \text{IVNSR}(P)$.

Corollary 3.4. *If $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$, then $\Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$ iff one is contained in other.*

Definition 3.5. Let $\Omega = \{(r, \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r), \bar{i}_{\Omega}(r), \bar{f}_{\Omega}(r)) : r \in P\}$ be an IVNS of a crisp ring $(P, +, \cdot)$. Also, let $[k_1, s_1]$, $[k_2, s_2]$ and $[k_3, s_3] \in \Psi(L)$. Then the crisp set $\Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$ is called a level set of IVNSR Ω , where for any $r \in \Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$ the following inequalities will hold: $\bar{t}_{\Omega}(r) \geq [k_1, s_1]$, $\bar{i}_{\Omega}(r) \leq [k_2, s_2]$, and $\bar{f}_{\Omega}(r) \leq [k_3, s_3]$.

Theorem 3.5. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring. Then $\Omega \in IVNSR(P)$ iff $\forall [k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3] \in \Psi(L)$ with $\bar{t}_\Omega(\theta_P) \geq [k_1, s_1]$, $\bar{i}_\Omega(\theta_P) \leq [k_2, s_2]$, and $\bar{f}_\Omega(\theta_P) \leq [k_3, s_3]$, $\Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$ is a crisp subring of $(P, +, \cdot)$ (assuming all the IVTN and IVSNs are idempotent).

Proof. Since, $\bar{t}_\Omega(\theta_P) \geq [k_1, s_1]$, $\bar{i}_\Omega(\theta_P) \leq [k_2, s_2]$, and $\bar{f}_\Omega(\theta_P) \leq [k_3, s_3]$, $\theta_P \in \Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$, i.e., $\Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$ is non-empty. Now, let $\Omega \in IVNSR(P)$ and $r, v \in \Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$. To show that, $(r - v)$ and $r \cdot v \in \Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$. Here,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_\Omega(r - v) &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)) \text{ [by Proposition 3.1]} \\ &\geq \bar{T}([k_1, s_1], [k_1, s_1]) \text{ [as } r, v \in \Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}] \\ &\geq [k_1, s_1] \text{ [as } \bar{T} \text{ is idempotent]} \end{aligned} \tag{3.19}$$

Again,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_\Omega(r \cdot v) &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)) \text{ [by Proposition 3.1]} \\ &\geq \bar{T}([k_1, s_1], [k_1, s_1]) \text{ [as } r, v \in \Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}] \\ &\geq [k_1, s_1] \text{ [as } \bar{T} \text{ is idempotent]} \end{aligned} \tag{3.20}$$

Similarly, we can show that

$$\bar{i}_\Omega(r - v) \leq [k_2, s_2], \tag{3.21}$$

$$\bar{i}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \leq [k_2, s_2], \tag{3.22}$$

$$\bar{f}_\Omega(r - v) \leq [k_3, s_3], \text{ and} \tag{3.23}$$

$$\bar{f}_\Omega(r \cdot v) \leq [k_3, s_3] \tag{3.24}$$

Hence, by Equations 3.19–3.24 $(r - v)$ and $r \cdot v \in \Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$, i.e., $\Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$ is a crisp subring of $(P, +, \cdot)$.

Conversely, let $\Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$ is a crisp subgroup of $(P, +, \cdot)$. To show that, $\Omega \in IVNSR(P)$.

Let $r, v \in P$, then there exists $[k_1, s_1] \in \Psi(L)$ such that $\bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)) = [k_1, s_1]$. So, $\bar{t}_\Omega(r) \geq [k_1, s_1]$ and $\bar{t}_\Omega(v) \geq [k_1, s_1]$. Also, let there exist $[k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3] \in \Psi(L)$ such that $\bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(v)) = [k_2, s_2]$ and $\bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(v)) = [k_3, s_3]$. Then $r, v \in \Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$.

Again, as $\Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$ is a crisp subring, $r - v \in \Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$ and $r \cdot v \in \Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$.

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_\Omega(r - v) &\geq [k_1, s_1] \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)) \text{ and} \end{aligned} \tag{3.25}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_\Omega(r \cdot v) &\geq [k_1, s_1] \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{t}_\Omega(v)) \end{aligned} \tag{3.26}$$

Similarly, we can prove that

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{i}_\Omega(r - v) &\leq [k_2, s_2] \\ &= \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(v)), \end{aligned} \tag{3.27}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{i}_\Omega(r \cdot v) &\leq [k_2, s_2] \\ &= \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(v)), \end{aligned} \tag{3.28}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{f}_\Omega(r - v) &\leq [k_3, s_3] \\ &= \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(v)), \text{ and} \end{aligned} \tag{3.29}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{f}_\Omega(r \cdot v) &\leq [k_3, s_3] \\ &= \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(v)) \end{aligned} \tag{3.30}$$

So, Equations 3.25–3.30 imply that Ω follows Proposition 3.1, i.e., $\Omega \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$. \square

Definition 3.6. Let Ω and Ω' be two IVNSs of two CSs P and R , respectively. Also, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a function. Then

- (i) image of Ω under l will be $l(\Omega) = \{(v, \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v), \bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v), \bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v)) : v \in R\}$, where $\bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v) = \bigvee_{s \in l^{-1}(v)} \bar{t}_\Omega(s)$, $\bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v) = \bigwedge_{s \in l^{-1}(v)} \bar{i}_\Omega(s)$, $\bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v) = \bigwedge_{s \in l^{-1}(v)} \bar{f}_\Omega(s)$. Wherefrom, if l is injective then $\bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v) = \bar{t}_\Omega(l^{-1}(v))$, $\bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v) = \bar{i}_\Omega(l^{-1}(v))$, $\bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v) = \bar{f}_\Omega(l^{-1}(v))$, and
- (ii) preimage of Ω' under l will be $l^{-1}(\Omega') = \{(r, \bar{t}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r), \bar{i}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r), \bar{f}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r)) : r \in R\}$, where $\bar{t}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r) = \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(l(r))$, $\bar{i}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r) = \bar{i}_{\Omega'}(l(r))$, $\bar{f}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r) = \bar{f}_{\Omega'}(l(r))$.

Theorem 3.6. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings. Also, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a ring isomorphism. If Ω is an IVNSR of P then $l(\Omega)$ is an IVNSR of R .

Proof. Let $v_1 = l(r_1)$ and $v_2 = l(r_2)$, where $r_1, r_2 \in P$ and $v_1, v_2 \in R$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1 - v_2) &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_1 - v_2)) \text{ [as } l \text{ is injective]} \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_1) - l^{-1}(v_2)) \text{ [as } l^{-1} \text{ is a homomorphism]} \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r_1 - r_2) \\
 &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega}(r_1), \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r_2)) \\
 &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_1)), \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_2))) \\
 &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1), \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v_2))
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.31}$$

Again,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1 \cdot v_2) &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_1 \cdot v_2)) \text{ [as } l \text{ is injective]} \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_1) \cdot l^{-1}(v_2)) \text{ [as } l^{-1} \text{ is a homomorphism]} \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r_1 \cdot r_2) \\
 &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega}(r_1), \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r_2)) \\
 &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_1)), \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_2))) \\
 &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1), \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v_2))
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.32}$$

Similarly,

$$\bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1 - v_2) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1), \bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v_2)), \tag{3.33}$$

$$\bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1 \cdot v_2) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1), \bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v_2)), \tag{3.34}$$

$$\bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1 - v_2) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1), \bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v_2)), \text{ and} \tag{3.35}$$

$$\bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1 \cdot v_2) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1), \bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v_2)) \tag{3.36}$$

Hence, Equations 3.31–3.36 imply that $l(\Omega)$ follows Proposition 3.1, i.e., $l(\Omega)$ is an IVNSR of R . \square

Theorem 3.7. *Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings. Also, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a ring homomorphism. If Ω' is an IVNSR of R then $l^{-1}(\Omega')$ is an IVNSR of P (Note that, l^{-1} may not be an inverse mapping but $l^{-1}(\Omega')$ is an inverse image of Ω').*

Proof. Let $v_1 = l(r_1)$ and $v_2 = l(r_2)$, where $r_1, r_2 \in P$ and $v_1, v_2 \in R$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{t}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1 - r_2) &= \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(l(r_1 - r_2)) \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(l(r_1) - l(r_2)) \text{ [as } l \text{ is a homomorphism]} \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(v_1 - v_2) \\
 &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega'}(v_1), \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(v_2)) \\
 &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega'}(l(r_1)), \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(l(r_2))) \\
 &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1), \bar{t}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_2))
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.37}$$

Again,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{t}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1 \cdot r_2) &= \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(l(r_1 \cdot r_2)) \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(l(r_1) \cdot l(r_2)) \text{ [as } l \text{ is a homomorphism]} \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(v_1 \cdot v_2) \\
 &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega'}(v_1), \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(v_2)) \\
 &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega'}(l(r_1)), \bar{t}_{\Omega'}(l(r_2))) \\
 &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1), \bar{t}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_2))
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.38}$$

Similarly,

$$\bar{i}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1 - r_2) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1), \bar{i}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_2))
 \tag{3.39}$$

$$\bar{i}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1 \cdot r_2) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1), \bar{i}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_2))
 \tag{3.40}$$

$$\bar{f}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1 - r_2) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1), \bar{f}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_2))
 \tag{3.41}$$

$$\bar{f}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1 \cdot r_2) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_1), \bar{f}_{l^{-1}(\Omega')}(r_2))
 \tag{3.42}$$

Hence, Equations 3.37–3.42 imply that $l^{-1}(\Omega')$ follows Proposition 3.1, i.e., $l^{-1}(\Omega')$ is an IVNSR of P . \square

Definition 3.7. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring and $\Omega \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$. Again, let $\bar{\sigma} = [\sigma_1, \sigma_2]$, $\bar{\tau} = [\tau_1, \tau_2]$, $\bar{\delta} = [\delta_1, \delta_2] \in \Psi(L)$. Then

(i) Ω is called a $(\bar{\sigma}, \bar{\tau}, \bar{\delta})$ -identity IVNSR over P , if $\forall r \in P$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_\Omega(r) &= \begin{cases} \bar{\sigma} & \text{if } r = \theta_P \\ [0, 0] & \text{if } r \neq \theta_P \end{cases}, \\ \bar{i}_\Omega(r) &= \begin{cases} \bar{\tau} & \text{if } r = \theta_P \\ [1, 1] & \text{if } r \neq \theta_P \end{cases}, \text{ and} \\ \bar{f}_\Omega(r) &= \begin{cases} \bar{\delta} & \text{if } r = \theta_P \\ [1, 1] & \text{if } r \neq \theta_P \end{cases}, \end{aligned}$$

where θ_P is the zero element of P .

(ii) Ω is called a $(\bar{\sigma}, \bar{\tau}, \bar{\delta})$ -absolute IVNSR over P , if $\forall r \in P$, $\bar{t}_\Omega(r) = \bar{\sigma}$, $\bar{i}_\Omega(r) = \bar{\tau}$, and $\bar{f}_\Omega(r) = \bar{\delta}$.

Theorem 3.8. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings and $\Omega \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$. Again, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a ring homomorphism. Then

(i) $l(\Omega)$ will be a $(\bar{\sigma}, \bar{\tau}, \bar{\delta})$ -identity IVNSR over R , if $\forall r \in P$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(r) &= \begin{cases} \bar{\sigma} & \text{if } r \in \text{Ker}(l) \\ [0, 0] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \\ \bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(r) &= \begin{cases} \bar{\tau} & \text{if } r \in \text{Ker}(l) \\ [1, 1] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \text{ and} \\ \bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(r) &= \begin{cases} \bar{\delta} & \text{if } r \in \text{Ker}(l) \\ [1, 1] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $l(\Omega)$ will be a $(\bar{\sigma}, \bar{\tau}, \bar{\delta})$ -absolute IVNSR over R , if Ω is a $(\bar{\sigma}, \bar{\tau}, \bar{\delta})$ -absolute IVNSR over P .

Proof. (i) Clearly, by Theorem 3.6 $l(\Omega) \in \text{IVNSR}(R)$. Let $r \in \text{Ker}(l)$, then $l(r) = \theta_R$.

So,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(\theta_R) &= \bar{t}_\Omega(l^{-1}(\theta_R)) \\ &= \bar{t}_\Omega(r) \\ &= \bar{\sigma} \end{aligned} \tag{3.43}$$

Similarly, we can show that

$$\bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(\theta_R) = \bar{\tau}, \text{ and} \tag{3.44}$$

$$\bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(\theta_R) = \bar{\delta} \tag{3.45}$$

Again, let $r \in P \setminus Ker(l)$ and $l(r) = v$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v) &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v)) \\ &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r) \\ &= [0, 0] \end{aligned} \tag{3.46}$$

Similarly, we can show that

$$\bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v) = [1, 1] \text{ and} \tag{3.47}$$

$$\bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v) = [1, 1] \tag{3.48}$$

Hence, by the Equations 3.43–3.48 $l(\Omega)$ is a $(\bar{\sigma}, \bar{\tau}, \bar{\delta})$ –identity IVNSR over R .

(ii) Let $l(r) = v$, for $r \in P$ and $v \in R$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v) &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v)) \\ &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r) \\ &= \bar{\sigma} \end{aligned} \tag{3.49}$$

Similarly, we can show that

$$\bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v) = \bar{\tau} \text{ and} \tag{3.50}$$

$$\bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v) = \bar{\delta} \tag{3.51}$$

Hence, by the Equations 3.48–3.51 $l(\Omega)$ is a $(\bar{\sigma}, \bar{\tau}, \bar{\delta})$ –absolute IVNSR over R . \square

3.1. Product of interval-valued neutrosophic subrings

Definition 3.8. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings. Again, let $\Omega_1 = \{(r, \bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{i}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{f}_{\Omega_1}(r)) : r \in P\}$ and $\Omega_2 = \{(v, \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v), \bar{i}_{\Omega_2}(v), \bar{f}_{\Omega_2}(v)) : v \in R\}$ are IVNSRs of P and R respectively. Then Cartesian product of Ω_1 and Ω_2 will be

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega &= \Omega_1 \times \Omega_2 \\ &= \left\{ \left((r, v), \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v)), \bar{I}(\bar{i}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{i}_{\Omega_2}(v)), \bar{F}(\bar{f}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{f}_{\Omega_2}(v))) \right) : (r, v) \in P \times R \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, product of 3 or more IVNSRs can be defined.

Theorem 3.9. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings with $\Omega_1 \in IVNSR(P)$ and $\Omega_2 \in IVNSR(R)$. Then $\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2$ is a IVNSR of $P \times R$.

Proof. Let $\Omega = \Omega_1 \times \Omega_2$ and $(r_1, v_1), (r_2, v_2) \in P \times R$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_\Omega((r_1, v_1) - (r_2, v_2)) &= \bar{t}_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2}((r_1 - r_2, v_1 - v_2)) \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r_1 - r_2), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v_1 - v_2)) \text{ [by Definition 3.8]} \\ &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r_1), \bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r_2)), \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v_1), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v_2))) \text{ [by Proposition 3.1]} \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r_1), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v_1)), \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r_2), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v_2))) \text{ [as } \bar{T} \text{ is associative]} \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r_1, v_1), \bar{t}_\Omega(r_2, v_2)) \end{aligned} \tag{3.52}$$

Again,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_\Omega((r_1, v_1) \cdot (r_2, v_2)) &= \bar{t}_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2}((r_1 \cdot r_2, v_1 \cdot v_2)) \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r_1 \cdot r_2), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v_1 \cdot v_2)) \text{ [by Definition 3.8]} \\ &\geq \bar{T}(\bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r_1), \bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r_2)), \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v_1), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v_2))) \text{ [by Proposition 3.1]} \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r_1), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v_1)), \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r_2), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v_2))) \text{ [as } \bar{T} \text{ is associative]} \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_\Omega(r_1, v_1), \bar{t}_\Omega(r_2, v_2)) \end{aligned} \tag{3.53}$$

Similarly, the followings can be shown

$$\bar{i}_\Omega((r_1, v_1) - (r_2, v_2)) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r_1, v_1), \bar{i}_\Omega(r_2, v_2)), \tag{3.54}$$

$$\bar{i}_\Omega((r_1, v_1) \cdot (r_2, v_2)) \leq \bar{I}(\bar{i}_\Omega(r_1, v_1), \bar{i}_\Omega(r_2, v_2)), \tag{3.55}$$

$$\bar{f}_\Omega((r_1, v_1) - (r_2, v_2)) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r_1, v_1), \bar{f}_\Omega(r_2, v_2)), \text{ and} \tag{3.56}$$

$$\bar{f}_\Omega((r_1, v_1) \cdot (r_2, v_2)) \leq \bar{F}(\bar{f}_\Omega(r_1, v_1), \bar{f}_\Omega(r_2, v_2)) \tag{3.57}$$

Hence, using Proposition 3.1 and by Equations 3.52–3.57 $\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(P \times R)$. \square

Corollary 3.10. *Let $\forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, $(P_i, +, \cdot)$ are crisp rings and $\Omega_i \in \text{IVNSR}(P_i)$. Then $\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2 \times \dots \times \Omega_n$ is a IVNSR of $P_1 \times P_2 \times \dots \times P_n$, where $n \in \mathbb{N}$.*

3.2. Subring of a interval-valued neutrosophic subgring

Definition 3.9. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$, where $\Omega_1 = \{(r, \bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{i}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{f}_{\Omega_1}(r)) : r \in P\}$ and $\Omega_2 = \{(r, \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r), \bar{i}_{\Omega_2}(r), \bar{f}_{\Omega_2}(r)) : r \in P\}$. Then Ω_1 is called a subring of Ω_2 if $\forall r \in P$, $\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r) \leq \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r)$, $\bar{i}_{\Omega_1}(r) \geq \bar{i}_{\Omega_2}(r)$, and $\bar{f}_{\Omega_1}(r) \geq \bar{f}_{\Omega_2}(r)$.

Theorem 3.11. *Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring and $\Omega \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$. Again, let Ω_1 and Ω_2 be two subrings of Ω . Then $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2$ is also a subring of Ω , assuming that all the IVTN and IVSNs are idempotent.*

Proof. Here, $\forall r \in P$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2}(r) &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r)) \\ &\leq \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega}(r), \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r)) \\ &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r) \text{ [as } \bar{T} \text{ is idempotent]} \end{aligned} \tag{3.58}$$

Similarly, as \bar{I} and \bar{F} are idempotent we can show that,

$$\bar{i}_{\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2}(r) \geq \bar{i}_{\Omega}(r) \text{ and} \tag{3.59}$$

$$\bar{f}_{\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2}(r) \geq \bar{f}_{\Omega}(r) \tag{3.60}$$

Hence, by Equations 3.58–3.60 $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2$ is a subring of Ω . \square

Theorem 3.12. *Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \in IVNSR(P)$ such that Ω_1 is a subring of Ω_2 . Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ is another crisp ring and $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a ring isomorphism. Then*

- (i) $l(\Omega_1)$ and $l(\Omega_2)$ are two IVNSRs over R and
- (ii) $l(\Omega_1)$ is a subring of $l(\Omega_2)$.

Proof. (i) can be proved by using Theorem 3.6.

(ii) Let $v = l(r)$, where $r \in P$ and $v \in R$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r) &\leq \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r) \text{ [as } \Omega_1 \text{ is a subring of } \Omega_2] \\ \Rightarrow \bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(l^{-1}(v)) &\leq \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(l^{-1}(v)) \\ \Rightarrow \bar{t}_{l(\Omega_1)}(v) &\leq \bar{t}_{l(\Omega_2)}(v) \end{aligned} \tag{3.61}$$

Similarly, we can prove that

$$\bar{i}_{l(\Omega_1)}(v) \geq \bar{i}_{l(\Omega_2)}(v) \text{ and} \tag{3.62}$$

$$\bar{f}_{l(\Omega_1)}(v) \geq \bar{f}_{l(\Omega_2)}(v) \tag{3.63}$$

Hence, by Equations 3.61–3.63 $l(\Omega_1)$ is a subring of $l(\Omega_2)$. \square

3.3. Interval-valued neutrosophic normal subrings

Definition 3.10. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring and Ω is an IVNS of P , where $\Omega = \{(r, \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r), \bar{i}_{\Omega}(r), \bar{f}_{\Omega}(r)) : r \in P\}$. Then Ω is called an IVNNSR over P if

- (i) Ω is an IVNSR of P and
- (ii) $\forall r, v \in P, \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r \cdot v) = \bar{t}_{\Omega}(v \cdot r), \bar{i}_{\Omega}(r \cdot v) = \bar{i}_{\Omega}(v \cdot r), \text{ and } \bar{f}_{\Omega}(r \cdot v) = \bar{f}_{\Omega}(v \cdot r)$.

The set of all IVNNSR of a crisp ring $(P, +, \cdot)$ will be denoted as $IVNNSR(P)$.

Example 3.11. Let $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ be the ring of integers with respect to usual addition and multiplication. Let $\Omega = \{(r, \bar{t}_\Omega(r), \bar{i}_\Omega(r), \bar{f}_\Omega(r)) : r \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ be an IVNS of \mathbb{Z} , where $\forall r \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_\Omega(r) &= \begin{cases} [0.67, 1] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} \\ [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}, \\ \bar{i}_\Omega(r) &= \begin{cases} [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} \\ [0.33, 0.5] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}, \text{ and} \\ \bar{f}_\Omega(r) &= \begin{cases} [0, 0] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} \\ [0, 0.33] & \text{if } r \in 2\mathbb{Z} + 1 \end{cases}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, if we consider minimum TN and maximum SNs, then $\Omega \in \text{IVNNSR}(\mathbb{Z})$.

Theorem 3.13. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring. If $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNNSR}(P)$, then $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNNSR}(P)$.

Proof. As $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$ by Theorem 3.2 $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNSR}(P)$. Again,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t}_{\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2}(r \cdot v) &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(r \cdot v), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(r \cdot v)) \\ &= \bar{T}(\bar{t}_{\Omega_1}(v \cdot r), \bar{t}_{\Omega_2}(v \cdot r)) \text{ [as } \Omega_1, \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNNSR}(P)] \\ &= \bar{t}_{\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2}(v \cdot r) \end{aligned} \tag{3.64}$$

Similarly,

$$\bar{i}_{\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2}(r \cdot v) = \bar{i}_{\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2}(v \cdot r) \tag{3.65}$$

$$\bar{f}_{\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2}(r \cdot v) = \bar{f}_{\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2}(v \cdot r) \tag{3.66}$$

Hence, $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNNSR}(P)$. \square

Remark 3.14. In general, if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \in \text{IVNNSR}(P)$, then $\Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2$ may not always be an IVNNSR of $(P, +, \cdot)$.

Remark 3.14 can be proved by Example 3.4.

Theorem 3.15. Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ be a crisp ring. Then $\Omega \in \text{IVNNSR}(P)$ iff $\forall [k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3] \in \Psi(L)$ with $\bar{t}_\Omega(\theta_P) \geq [k_1, s_1]$, $\bar{i}_\Omega(\theta_P) \leq [k_2, s_2]$, and $\bar{f}_\Omega(\theta_P) \leq [k_3, s_3]$, $\Omega_{([k_1, s_1], [k_2, s_2], [k_3, s_3])}$ is a crisp normal subring of $(P, +, \cdot)$ (assuming all the IVTN and IVSNs are idempotent).

Proof. This can be proved using Theorem 3.5. \square

Theorem 3.16. *Let $(P, +, \cdot)$ and $(R, +, \cdot)$ be two crisp rings. Also, let $l : P \rightarrow R$ be a ring isomorphism. If Ω is an IVNNSR of P then $l(\Omega)$ is an IVNNSR of R .*

Proof. As Ω is an IVNSR of P by Theorem 3.6 $l(\Omega)$ is an IVNSR of R . Let $l(r_1) = v_1$ and $l(r_2) = v_2$, where $r_1, r_2 \in P$ and $v_1, v_2 \in R$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1 \cdot v_2) &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_1 \cdot v_2)) \text{ [as } l \text{ is injective]} \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_1) \cdot l^{-1}(v_2)) \text{ [as } l^{-1} \text{ is a homomorphism]} \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r_1 \cdot r_2) \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(r_2 \cdot r_1) \text{ [as } \Omega \text{ is an IVNNSR of } P\text{]} \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_2) \cdot l^{-1}(v_1)) \\
 &= \bar{t}_{\Omega}(l^{-1}(v_2 \cdot v_1)) \\
 &= \bar{t}_{l(\Omega)}(v_2 \cdot v_1)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.67}$$

Similarly,

$$\bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1 \cdot v_2) = \bar{i}_{l(\Omega)}(v_2 \cdot v_1) \text{ and} \tag{3.68}$$

$$\bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v_1 \cdot v_2) = \bar{f}_{l(\Omega)}(v_2 \cdot v_1) \tag{3.69}$$

Hence, by Equations 3.67–3.69 $l(\Omega)$ is an IVNNSR of R . \square

4. Conclusions

As interval-valued neutrosophic environment is more general than regular one, we have adopted it and defined the notions of interval-valued neutrosophic subring and its normal version. Also, we have analyzed some homomorphic properties of these newly defined notions. Again, we have studied product of two interval-valued neutrosophic subrings. Furthermore, we have provided some essential theories to study some of their algebraic structures. These newly introduced notions have potentials to become fruitful research areas. For instance, soft set theory can be implemented and the notion of interval-valued neutrosophic soft subring can be defined.

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